

METHODS OF WORKING WITH A CHILDREN'S CHOIR

Jalilova Kamolakhon Shukhratjon kizi

National Pop Art Institute named after Botir Zakirov under the State
Conservatory of Uzbekistan

Teacher of the department "Training of pedagogues of pop
performance".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12090295>

Abstract: Music is a form of education. That is why in many countries of the world, children are taught the art of music. Choral, vocal and musical lessons are conducted for children in schools and in various clubs. Psychologists of the world also approve of this and say that it increases the child's mental activity, self-awareness and curiosity.

Key word: Music, vocal, children, choir, singing, voice, tessitura, art, treble, mutation, sound.

Introduction:

Every leader who works with children should be able to imagine not only their current situation, but also the situation of the team in 2-3 years. For this, it is necessary to ensure that the children do not disperse, to organize the work with the aim of long years, not seasonally. In order to properly organize the vocal-choir group, it is necessary to divide the children according to their age and voice characteristics. Because the working capacity of young children is lower than that of middle-aged children, and the vocal apparatus gets tired quickly. The interest of younger children may not be of interest to middle-aged children.

Types of children's choir:

- Children's vocal choir group, children 7-9 years old.
- Middle-aged children's vocal choir group, children aged 10-14.
- Choir of high school students unites teenagers aged 14-17.

When the child reaches a certain age, the child from the small choir group is transferred to the middle group, and from the middle choir group to the large choir group. Only then will children develop.

It is necessary for the leader to develop the rules of procedure in the vocal-choir team:

- Participants of the vocal-choir team must regularly participate in training.
- Lessons can be left only for good reason.
- You should come to the training on time without being late.
- It is required to be active and attentive during training.
- It is necessary to create a cheerful mood in the team. Only then will children look forward to their training regularly.

In order to further strengthen the activity of the vocal-choir team, it is very important that the leader, in addition to his duties, regularly communicates with parents. Some parents do not allow their children to participate in the choir, regardless of their wishes. According to them, choir is completely foreign to children. The leader of the choir should be able to put an end to such concepts. They should be interested in choral art.

Characteristics of children's voices. Children's voices are distinguished by lightness and sonority. According to their characteristics, they are divided into treble and alt. Treble is the highest voice of children. The 1st octave goes from the note "Do" to the note "Sol" in the 2nd octave.

The emotional richness of children's voices brightens the performance and increases expressiveness. In terms of tessitura, children's voices will find it easier to sing if the middle width of the diapason is used. When using high sounds, it is necessary to speak slowly. If low sounds are used a lot, the voice becomes strained. One of the most important tasks of the leader of the choir is to ensure that all the sounds of the children's vocal range, including vowels, are pronounced evenly. It is necessary to pay attention to the correctness of articulation and pronunciation while chanting. When singing in the choir, it is advisable to check each of the children individually. A choirmaster should not tire children's voices and take care of them. When singing a hymn, one should pay attention to the child's posture, because many children raise their shoulders while singing, and breathe as if they are choking. This type of breathing has a negative effect on the child's body. Children should be taught music in order to achieve high performance skills. The leader of the choir should devote 10-15 minutes to the musical education of the children in each session.

It is good to conduct exercises in the form of games so that children do not get bored. In the process of teaching each song, if you give information about the song and explain its main idea, the children will try to tell the song in their own character. In the process of working with a children's choir, canons can also be used. It helps to develop polyphonic skills in children. Adding musical movements to each song makes children more interested in the chorus.

Of course, when choosing a repertoire for children, it is chosen according to their age. Seasonal, festive, patriotic songs, humorous and cheerful songs are selected. The composers who contributed to the development of the children's choir, i.e. the composers loved by our people: Shermat Yormatov, Avaz Mansurov, Dilorom Omonullayeva, Anor Nazarov, Nadim Norkhojaye, Khurshida Khasanova and others.

Conclusion:

In short, the level of success of a children's vocal choir depends on the level of its organization. It is necessary that the content be stable. Only then will the choir become a creative team capable of performing choral works of different styles and complexity.

References:

1. Sharafiyeva N. Chorology. Literary and art publishing house named after G. Ghulam. T., 1987.
2. Roziyev Sh. Khorshnoslik Literary and Art Publishing House named after G. Ghulam. T., 1987.
3. Sharafiyeva N. Choir class. T., 2005.
4. Jumayeva L.Kh. From the history of Uzbek choral music. T., 2000.
5. L. Dzhumayeva, N. Sharafiyeva Choir Class and Chamber Choir. T., 2017.

